

On the Consistency of the Shortest Hamiltonian Path Test

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Abstract

Introduced by Biswas et al. (2014), the shortest Hamiltonian path (SHP) test is a popular non-parametric, multivariate 2-sample test which has the much-desired property that it is exactly distribution-free under the null hypothesis. The test constructs a shortest Hamiltonian path on the pooled sample and counts the number of edges connecting points from different samples. For similar distributions, the test statistic should be relatively large, and for dissimilar distributions, the test statistic should be small. The nature of the SHP makes it quite similar to path construction for the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP), and exact calculation of the SHP is nondeterministic polynomial (NP) complete. In this paper, we use TSP approximation methods to approximate the SHP. We prove that the SHP test is universally consistent under this implementation, that is, the power of the tests converges to 1, as the samples sizes go to infinity, for all fixed alternatives.

Keywords: Graph Based Tests, Consistency, Distribution Free Tests, High Dimensional Tests, Nonparametric Statistics

Statements and Declarations: The author has no conflict of interest nor pertinent funding information to declare.

1 Introduction

Two-sample testing of multivariate distributions is a classical problem in statistical inference. The problem considers two independent samples: $X_1, \dots, X_m \sim F$ and $Y_1, \dots, Y_n \sim G$ with F, G being unknown distributions in \mathbb{R}^d . The two-sample problem tests the hypotheses of

$$H_0 : F = G \quad vs. \quad H_1 : F \neq G$$

Classical nonparametric tests for $d = 1$ include the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (Smirnov, 1939), Wald-Wolfowitz runs test (Wald & Wolfowitz, 1940), and Mann-Whitney rank test (Mann & Whitney, 1947). Multivariate non-parametric tests for $d > 1$ are graph-based and include the Friedman-Rafsky test (Friedman & Rafsky, 1979), Rosenbaum's Crossmatch test (Rosenbaum, 2005), shortest Hamiltonian path (SHP) test (Biswas, Mukhopadhyay, & Ghosh, 2014), and more recently, multivariate rank based tests based on optimal transport (Nabarun & Sen, 2019). The latter three are notable for being exactly distribution free with known distributions for their test statistics. The Friedman-Rafsky constructs a minimum spanning tree graph \mathcal{G} on the pooled sample of $\{X_1, \dots, X_m\} \cup \{Y_1, \dots, Y_n\}$ (Friedman & Rafsky, 1979). The test statistic R is based on the cardinality of edges connecting points of distinct samples, that is, edges connecting a point from $\{X_1, \dots, X_m\}$ to a point in $\{Y_1, \dots, Y_n\}$ (Friedman & Rafsky, 1979). Under H_0 , R should be relatively large, and the test rejects H_0 for small values of R . Henze and Penrose proved consistency against fixed alternatives for the Friedman-Rafsky test and that it is asymptotically distribution free under H_0 (Henze & Penrose, 1999).

The Crossmatch test and SHP test are two well known graph based nonparametric exactly distribution free tests. Rosenbaum’s Crossmatch test (Rosenbaum, 2005) constructs a minimal weight non-bipartite graph \mathcal{G} . Similar to Friedman-Rafsky test, the Crossmatch test statistic is based on the cardinality of edges connecting points from separate samples. Notably, (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016) proved general consistency of the Crossmatch test with methods similar to that of (Henze & Penrose, 1999). More recently, a third exactly distribution free test has been developed, as (Nabarun & Sen, 2019) developed a multivariate rank based test using optimal transport to compare the distributions F, G .

The other multivariate, exactly distribution free test is the SHP test. A Hamiltonian path \mathcal{H} connects all points of a graph such that no vertex has degree greater than 2, thus it is the set of $N - 1$ edges that link all N points together such that no point has degree greater than 2 (Biswas et al., 2014). Using the same notation as (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), let $Z_i = X_i$ for $i \leq m$ and $Z_{m+j} = Y_j$ for $1 \leq j \leq n$ with $N = m + n$. The SHP test involves constructing a Hamiltonian path \mathcal{H}^* that connects all points of the pooled sample $\{Z_1, \dots, Z_N\}$, whilst minimizing the sum of the edge lengths (Biswas et al., 2014). The associated test statistic $T_{m,n}$ counts the number of edges connecting separate distributions and is defined as

$$T_{m,n} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} U_i,$$

where U_i is an indicator variable that is supported if the i^{th} edge connects nodes from different samples. In practice, the SHP was demonstrated to have significantly better power than the Friedman-Rafsky test and Crossmatch test among other tests across a wide range of low and high dimensional problems and ranging in settings from sonar to gene markers (Biswas et al., 2014).

The shortest Hamiltonian path test, like the Crossmatch test, is an exactly distribution free test with a tractable finite sample null distribution. This separates it from other non-parametric multivariate tests that must be calibrated with permutations. Combined with the demonstrated successful applications of this test, the shortest Hamiltonian path test is certainly an appealing test for implementation purposes. However, the consistency of this test has yet to be proven.

In this paper, we prove general consistency for the shortest Hamiltonian path test using methods developed in (Henze & Penrose, 1999) for the Friedman-Rafsky test and (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016) for the Crossmatch test.

1.1 Outline

Section 2 describes the exact implementation of the SHP test with Section 2.1 specifying how to approximate the SHP, and Section 2.2 states the null distribution. In Section 3, we state Theorem 1 of convergence to the Henze-Penrose divergence, which gives consistency. We then state Lemma 1 and Lemma 2, which are required to prove Theorem 1. Finally, we prove Theorem 1 using Lemma 1 and Lemma 2. In Section 3.1, we prove Lemma 1 with the assistance of a Lemma 1.1, which is proven in Section 3.1.1. In Section 3.2, we prove Lemma 2 with an additional assumption that long edges do not exist. The assumption of the nonexistence of long edges is justified in Section 3.2.1.

2 Implementation of the Shortest Hamiltonian Path Test

We utilise a similar setup to (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016). Given two independent samples of $\{X_1, \dots, X_m \sim F\}$ and $\{Y_1, \dots, Y_n \sim G\}$ with F, G being their respective distribution functions supported on \mathbb{R}^d . We seek to test

$$H_0 : F = G \text{ vs. } H_1 : F \neq G.$$

We will also assume that

$$\frac{m}{m+n} \rightarrow \rho \in (0, 1). \tag{1}$$

Following the regime of (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), for the pooled sample $\mathbf{Z} = \{Z_1, \dots, Z_N\}$ where $Z_i = X_i$ for $i \leq m$ and $Z_{m+j} = Y_j$ for $1 \leq j \leq n$ with $N = m + n$, let \mathcal{G} be a complete graph on

$$\mathbf{Z} = \{Z_1, \dots, Z_N\}.$$

Every Hamiltonian path \mathcal{H} on \mathcal{G} can be associated with an order N permutation $\sigma \in S_N$, where the mapping $\sigma(i) = j$ indicates that the i^{th} node of \mathcal{H} is Z_j , and for all $1 \leq i \leq N-1$, there exists an edge on the path \mathcal{H} between $Z_{\sigma(i)}$ and $Z_{\sigma(i+1)}$. We can define the length, $\Lambda(\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{G})$, of a Hamiltonian path \mathcal{H} on graph \mathcal{G} to be

$$\Lambda(\mathcal{H}, \mathcal{G}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \|Z_{\sigma(i)} - Z_{\sigma(i+1)}\|, \quad (2)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ is an arbitrary metric. \mathcal{H}^* is the SHP associated with the permutation $\sigma^* \in S_N$ that minimizes (2). The SHP test statistic of

$$T_{m,n} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} U_i \quad (3)$$

is then calculated on \mathcal{H}^* , where U_i is the indicator variable on the edge between $\sigma^*(i)$ and $\sigma^*(i+1)$, which is supported if the edge connects points between different samples. The number of edges connecting separate samples should be large if $F = G$, thus the test rejects the null hypotheses for small values $T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}^*)$.

2.1 Shortest Hamiltonian Path Approximation

We must construct a SHP. The SHP is very similar in nature to the Traveling Salesmen Problem (TSP) (Biswas et al., 2014), which is challenging to exactly compute. Hence, we turn to approximation methods for the TSP to make the SHP approximation. In place of the original approximation algorithm presented in (Biswas et al., 2014), we implement the well known Approx-TSP-TOUR algorithm iteratively (Cormen, Leiserson, Rivest, & Stein, 2009) using a hypercube construction similar to (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016). The version of the Approx-TSP-TOUR we use is a more concrete version of the one presented in (Cormen et al., 2009).

Algorithm 1 Approx-TSP-TOUR

1. Construct minimum spanning tree T on $\{z_1, \dots, z_g\}$ using Kruskal's algorithm (Cormen et al., 2009)
 2. Select the node with the greatest degree with ties being broken by selecting the node with the least first coordinate to be the root. Ties can be broken by considering higher coordinates.
 3. Consider the list l of vertices, ordered according to when they are first visited in a leftmost depth first search (DFS) tree traversal of T based off the first coordinate. The DFS starts from the root defined in Step 2.
 4. Depth first search usually visits nodes multiple times, which is incompatible with the construction of a Hamiltonian path. Thus, after the first instance of a vertex, we delete all following instances of said vertex. This procedure yields a list l of vertices with no duplicates.
 5. The SHP, denoted \mathcal{H}^* , on $\{z_1, \dots, z_k\}$ is the set of edges connecting the adjacent vertices of the list l .
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We will use this algorithm iteratively to approximate the SHP. For a set of points $P = \{p_1, \dots, p_k\} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ with $d \geq 2$. The algorithm proceeds as follows:

Fig. 1 Algorithm in $d = 2$ and $\tau = 6$ (a) Initial distribution of points (b) The square has more than 6 points, thus it is divided into quadrants (c) The upper right square has more than 6 points, thus it is further divided (d) Approx-TSP-TOUR within each square yield an approximation of the shortest path within each square (e) Connection of the paths within the quadrants of the upper right square (g) Connection of the paths within the quadrants of the squares in the 2×2 grid leads to the final connection

Algorithm 2 SHP-Approx

1. Let $p_{i,j}$ be the j^{th} component of p_k . Set $M = \sup_{1 \leq i \leq k} \sup_{1 \leq j \leq d} |p_{i,j}|$, $S = \inf_{s \in \mathbb{Z}^+} \{s : 2^s \geq M\}$.
 2. Starting with the hypercube $[-2^S, 2^S]^d$, we divide the cube into 2^d equal sized hypercubes of side length 2^S .
 3. For each hypercube generated, we count the number of distinct points contained within it. For an arbitrary pre-selected constant τ . If the generated hypercube has less than or equal to τ distinct points, we stop dividing the hypercube. If the generated hypercube has more than τ distinct points, we further divide it into 2^d equal sized hypercubes, that is if the cube of length 2^{S-t} has greater than τ distinct points, we divide it into 2^d equal sized hypercubes of side length $2^{S-(t+1)}$. Fig. 1 illustrates an example of SHP-Approx. Fig. 1 (a) illustrates initial distribution of points, and since it has more than $\tau = 6$ within the square, Fig. 1 (b) illustrates the division of the original square into 4 squares.
 4. We apply Step 3 to each hypercube until each hypercube contains at most τ points. Let us define l as the number of iterations it takes from the original $[-2^S, 2^S]^d$ hypercube until each hypercube has at most τ points. Since the first iterations takes the side length from 2^{S+1} to 2^S , if it takes l iterations, the smallest cube has side length $2^{S-(l-1)}$. Fig. 1 (c) illustrates further division of the upper right square, as it has more than 6 points.
 5. Within a cube of at most τ points, the Approx-TSP-TOUR algorithm is run to connect the points to form a path, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (d).
 6. The paths within the 2^d equal sized hypercubes of length $2^{S-(l+1)}$ contained within a hypercube of length 2^{S-l} can be connected into a single path in the following manner. Define the $\{Z_1, \dots, Z_{2^d}\}$ as the center points of the 2^d length $2^{S-(l+1)}$ hypercubes. Point Z_i will be discounted if there is not a path contained in the i^{th} hypercube. The Approx-TSP-TOUR is run on the points of $\{Z_1, \dots, Z_{2^d}\}$ that represent occupied hypercubes. The edges of the Approx-TSP-TOUR dictate how to connect the paths within the length $2^{S-(l+1)}$ hypercubes. For concreteness sake, the terminal point with the greatest first component will be added to the terminal point of the subsequent path with greatest first component with ties being broken by considering further components.
 7. Starting with the smallest hypercubes of length $2^{S-(l+1)}$, step 6 is repeated until a singular path is formed, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (e). Fig. 1 (f) illustrates the final connection.
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In Figure 1, we illustrate how SHP-Approx works in $d = 2$.

2.2 Test Statistic and Distribution

The SHP test statistic (Biswas et al., 2014), $T_{m,n} = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} U_i$, has null distribution for the evens:

$$\mathbb{P}_0(T_{m,n} = 2k) = \frac{2 \binom{m-1}{k-1} \binom{n-1}{k-1}}{\binom{N}{m}} \quad k = 1, \dots, m \wedge n$$

and for odds:

$$\mathbb{P}_0(T_{m,n} = 2k - 1) = \frac{\binom{m-1}{k-1} \binom{n-1}{k-2} + \binom{m-1}{k-2} \binom{n-1}{k-1}}{\binom{N}{m}} \quad k = 2, \dots, m \wedge n + 1$$

For F, G that differ vastly, $T_{m,n}$ should be quite small, so for small values of $T_{m,n}$, we reject the null.

2.3 Normal Limit

Note that the null distribution of the SHP test is the same as that of the Wald and Wolfowitz's runs test (Wald & Wolfowitz, 1940). This is because the SHP test statistic counts the number of edges across the 2-samples, which is equivalent to counting the number of runs along the SHP. As a result, the asymptotic distribution of the SHP test under H_0 is the same as the Wald-Wolfowitz's run test (Wald & Wolfowitz, 1940). In particular, one has

$$\sqrt{N} \left[\frac{T_{m,n}}{N} - 2\rho(1 - \rho) \right] \xrightarrow{D} N(0, 4\rho^2(1 - \rho)^2) \quad (4)$$

where ρ is defined in (1).

3 Consistency

In this paper, we establish the consistency of the SHP test under fixed alternatives. Specifically, we prove the following result.

Theorem 1. *For a shortest Hamiltonian path \mathcal{H}^* approximated as in Section 2.1 in the limiting regime of (1),*

$$\frac{T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}^*)}{m+n} \xrightarrow{a.s.} 2 \int \frac{\rho(1 - \rho)F(z)G(z)}{\rho F(z) + (1 - \rho)G(z)} dz \quad (5)$$

The proof of Theorem 1 follows exactly from the proof of Theorem 2 of (Henze & Penrose, 1999). We prove the necessary analogous lemmas for Theorem 2 of (Henze & Penrose, 1999). We will first start by proving Lemma 1, which states that the test statistic does not change much by the addition of a point. This is stated in the following lemma which is proved in Section 3.1. The following Lemma 1 is analogous to Lemma 1 presented in (Henze & Penrose, 1999).

Lemma 1. *Let $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_m\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$ be disjoint sets in \mathbb{R}^d , and x be an additional point that is either from F or G . There exists constant γ for such that*

$$|T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(X \cup Y \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(X \cup Y))| \leq \gamma \quad (6)$$

Following (Henze & Penrose, 1999), we seek to prove an analogous result to Proposition 1 of (Henze & Penrose, 1999). To do, we will follow the technique of (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016). Proposition 1 of (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016) is an analogous result to Proposition 1 of (Henze & Penrose, 1999). The technique to prove Proposition 1 of (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016) required the additional statement that edges of length longer than $N^{-1/d}$ are unlikely to occur in the SHP. (Note that the distance between a sample point and its closest point in the sample is $O(N^{-1/d})$). The following Lemma 2 is analogous to Proposition 1 in both (Henze & Penrose, 1999) and (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016). The proof of Lemma 2 will be presented in Section 3.2, and the proof of the non-existence of long edges is proved in Section 3.2.1.

Lemma 2. For $\phi, \phi_1, \phi_2, \dots$ distribution functions with the same support such that $\frac{\phi_t}{\phi} \rightarrow 1$ uniformly on the set $\{z \in \mathbb{R}^d \mid \phi(z) > 0\}$. Let $\mathbb{Z}_N = \{Z_{1,N}, \dots, Z_{N,N}\}$ be IID with distribution ϕ_t . Let $h : \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow [0, 1]$ a measurable function such that almost all points $z \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is Lebesgue point of $h(z, \cdot)\phi(\cdot)$. We have

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq N} h(Z_{i,N}, Z_{j,N}) \mathbf{I}_{[Z_{i,N} \rightarrow Z_{j,N} \in \mathcal{H}]} \right] = \frac{\delta}{2} \int h(z, z) \phi(z) dz = \int h(z, z) \phi(z) dz \quad (7)$$

Where δ is defined as $\Delta(Z_{1,N}; \mathcal{H}(\mathbb{Z}_N)) \xrightarrow{P} \delta$. Note that $\Delta(Z_{1,N}; \mathcal{H}(\mathbb{Z}_N))$ is defined as the degree of $Z_{1,N}$ in the graph $\mathcal{H}(\mathbb{Z}_N)$. Given that in any Hamiltonian path, all nodes have degree 2 (except the terminal nodes which have degree 1). Thus we have $\Delta(Z_{1,N}; \mathcal{H}(\mathbb{Z}_N)) \xrightarrow{P} 2$, hence $\delta = 2$.

Proof of Theorem 1. In (Henze & Penrose, 1999), apart from Lemma 1 and Proposition 1, the proof of Theorem 2 is graph structure independent, and we have proven analogous statements for the SHP test for Lemma 1 and Proposition 1 of (Henze & Penrose, 1999) in the form of (6) and (7), respectively. Thus the proof of (5) can follow exactly from the proof of Theorem 2 in (Henze & Penrose, 1999). Specifically, we get

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} U_i}{m+n} \xrightarrow{a.s.} 2 \int \frac{\rho(1-\rho)F(z)G(z)}{\rho F(z) + (1-\rho)G(z)} dz. \quad (8)$$

In the definition of the test statistic (3), the test statistic differs from 1 on the numerator of the right hand side of (8).

$$\frac{T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}^*)}{m+n} = \frac{1}{m+n} + \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} U_i}{m+n} \xrightarrow{a.s.} 2 \int \frac{\rho(1-\rho)F(z)G(z)}{\rho F(z) + (1-\rho)G(z)} dz. \quad (9)$$

Consistency follows from comparing $\frac{T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}^*)}{m+n}$ in the scenarios of $F \neq G$ and $F = G$. As stated in (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), the limit of (9) is strictly smaller when $F \neq G$ than when $F = G$, hence, the test is consistent. More specifically, considering the latter case when $F = G$,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}^*)}{m+n} &\xrightarrow{a.s.} 2 \int \frac{\rho(1-\rho)F(z)F(z)}{\rho F(z) + (1-\rho)F(z)} dz = 2\rho(1-\rho) \int \frac{F(z)F(z)}{\rho F(z) + (1-\rho)F(z)} dz \\ &2\rho(1-\rho) \int \frac{F(z)F(z)}{\rho F(z) + (1-\rho)F(z)} dz = 2\rho(1-\rho) \int \frac{F(z)}{\rho + (1-\rho)} dz = 2\rho(1-\rho). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the test is asymptotically consistent. \square

3.1 Robustness of Shortest Hamiltonian Path Approximations

Lemma 1. Let $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_m\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$ be disjoint sets in \mathbb{R}^d , and x be an additional point that is either from F or G . There exists constant γ for such that

$$|T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(X \cup Y \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(X \cup Y))| \leq \gamma \quad (10)$$

Proof Sketch. In order to limit the difference between the test statistic on $X \cup Y$ and the test statistic on $X \cup Y \cup \{x\}$, it is ideal for $\{x\}$ or the path containing $\{x\}$ to be incorporated to the interior of another path, as only the terminal points of a path interact with other paths. Once, $\{x\}$ or the path containing $\{x\}$ is contained in the interior, the linkages between subhypercubes should be the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$, thus forming the same edges.

We will obtain an upper bound on difference between test statistics of hypercubes until $\{x\}$ or the path containing $\{x\}$ to be incorporated to the interior of another path. To do so, we consider the ways that $\{x\}$ can be added to a previously constructed hypercube and analyze through cases the difference in test statistics of larger and larger hypercubes containing $\{x\}$ until $\{x\}$ or the path containing $\{x\}$ to be incorporated to the interior of another path.

Fig. 2 The green point is the new point added to the previous set (a) Scenario 1 (b) Scenario 2 (c) Scenario 3

Once $\{x\}$ or the path containing $\{x\}$ to be incorporated to the interior of another path, we will use induction to prove there is no further difference in test statistics. Lastly, we will also consider the edge case in which $\{x\}$ is an extreme point and is not incorporated into the previously constructed hypercube. \square

Proof. For the remainder of this proof, we use $\mathcal{H}(X)$ to represent the Hamiltonian path on the points of hypercube X using the approximation methods listed in [Section 2.1](#). In addition for a hypercube X , we refer to the 2^d hypercubes that comprise X as subhypercubes of X . To compute an upper bound on the difference between the test statistics, we must compare the paths generated, namely $\mathcal{H}(X \cup Y)$ and $\mathcal{H}(X \cup Y \cup \{x\})$. To do so, we will analyze the effect of the addition $\{x\}$ on the resultant path. If $\{x\}$ is incorporated into the same $[-2^S, 2^S]^d$ cube that was generated to contain $X \cup Y$, then the only difference between the hypercubes formed for $X \cup Y$ and the hypercubes formed for $X \cup Y \cup \{x\}$ is where the single point $\{x\}$ is incorporated. $\{x\}$ can only be added to one hypercube, so the other hypercubes are unaffected. More specifically, the addition can only occur in one of the following scenarios:

Scenario 1: Addition of $\{x\}$ into a hypercube C^* with with less than τ points previously. Scenario 1 is illustrated in Fig. 2 (a). Given $\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})$ has at most $\tau - 1$ edges since $C^* \cup \{x\}$ has at most τ points once $\{x\}$ has been added.

$$|T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^*))| \leq \tau - 1 \quad (11)$$

Scenario 2: Addition of $\{x\}$ into a hypercube C that was previously empty. Scenario 2 is illustrated in Fig. 2 (b). Let C^* be the smallest hypercube that has a subhypercube that contains C and another occupied subhypercube that does not contain C . Given it takes at most $2^d - 1$ edges to link the paths within the 2^d subhypercubes that comprise C^* to form $\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})$. The paths of the subhypercubes are unaffected with the exception of the subhypercube containing C , and the path of subhypercube containing C just contains $\{x\}$. The difference between the edge sets of $\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})$ and $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ comes from how the subhypercubes are linked, as $\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})$ must link together a previously unoccupied subhypercube. There are at most $2^d - 1$ edges to connect the 2^d subhypercubes, hence

$$|T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^*))| \leq 2^d - 1 \quad (12)$$

Scenario 3: Addition of $\{x\}$ into a hypercube C^* with exactly τ points previously. Scenario 2 is illustrated in Fig. 2 (c). We must continually divide C^* to get subhypercubes that each contain less than or equal to τ points. Given that $\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})$ will have exactly τ edges since C^* has exactly $\tau + 1$ points.

$$|T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^*))| \leq \tau \quad (13)$$

From (12) and (13), we have that the upper bound of the difference in test statistics when $\{x\}$ is added to C^* is $(2^d - 1) \vee \tau$

$$|T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^*))| \leq (2^d - 1) \vee \tau \quad (14)$$

Scenario is illustrated in Fig. 2 (c) The plan is to work up from C^* by linking paths within hypercubes together iteratively until there is single path in the $[-2^S, 2^S]^d$ hypercube. To study the difference in statistics, we will decompose the Hamiltonian path $\mathcal{H}(X)$; namely, we can condition the edge set of $\mathcal{H}(X)$ depending on if the edge connects paths between the 2^d different subhypercubes of X or if the edge connects points within a single of the 2^d subhypercubes of X . Let us define $E(\mathcal{H}(X))$ as the the edge set of $\mathcal{H}(X)$ (a Hamiltonian path of the hypercube X), $\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(X))$ as the set of edges that connect paths between the 2^d different subhypercubes of X , and $\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(X))$ as the set of edges that connect points within the individual 2^d subhypercubes of X . ($\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H})$ for between and $\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H})$ for within). We have

$$E(\mathcal{H}) = \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}) \cup \tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}) \quad (15)$$

For the remainder of this proof, we will refer to C^{k*} for $k \geq 2$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ as the smallest hypercube such that one of its 2^d subhypercubes contains $C^{(k-1)*}$ and another of its 2^d subhypercubes is occupied and does not contain C^* .

3.2 Second Level Hypercube ($k = 2$)

Now considering the difference in test statistics for C^{**} can write using (15).

$$T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**})) = T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**}))) + T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**})))$$

Using the triangle inequality

$$\begin{aligned} \left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**})) \right| &\leq \left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**}))) \right| + \\ &\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**}))) \right| \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and more generally for $k \geq 2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*})) \right| &\leq \left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*}))) \right| + \\ &\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*}))) \right| \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

We can further decompose $\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**}))$ into a summation of the subhypercubes of C^{**}

$$\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**})) = \sum_{i=1}^{2^d} \tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**})_i)$$

, where $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})_i$ denotes the path of the i^{th} subhypercube of C^{**} . Using the Triangle Inequality,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**}))) \right| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{2^d} \left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**})_i)) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\})_i)) \right| \quad (18)$$

There is no difference from how $\mathcal{H}(C^* \cup \{x\})$ is added into $\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\})$, as C^* was previously occupied before the addition of $\{x\}$, thus TSP-APPROX-tour on the center points of the occupied subhypercubes of C^{**} returns the same path. There are two cases for how $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$. In Case 1, $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$, and in Case 2, $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is

incorporated into the terminal portion of $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$.

Case 1: If $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into the interior $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$, as the center point of the subhypercube containing C^* is not a terminal point when APPROX-TSP-tour is run on the center points of the occupied subhypercubes of C^{**} . Excluding the subhypercube containing C^* , the remaining $2^d - 1$ subhypercubes of C^{**} are unaffected by addition of $\{x\}$, thus the paths of $2^d - 1$ of the subhypercubes are the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$, hence all terms of the summation on the right hand side of (18) are 0 except the subhypercube containing C^* which is bounded above by $(2^d - 1) \vee \tau$. Thus,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\}))) \right| \leq (2^d - 1) \vee \tau. \quad (19)$$

Given our definition of C^* , the subhypercube of C^{**} containing C^* was already occupied, because C^* was occupied prior to addition of $\{x\}$. Thus, only the 2 edges that may be different are the two needed to connect $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ to the rest of $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$. All other edges are the same, as they connect the same paths of the same subhypercubes of $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$ before and after addition of $\{x\}$, hence

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**}))) \right| \leq 2 \quad (20)$$

Thus, by substituting (19) and (20) into (16),

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**})) \right| \leq ((2^d - 1) \vee \tau) + 2 = (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (21)$$

Case 2: If $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated at the terminal portion of $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$, as the center point of the subhypercube containing C^* is a terminal point when APPROX-TSP-tour is run on the center points of the occupied subhypercubes of C^{**} . Again, the subhypercubes of C^{**} that do not contain C^* are unaffected by the addition of $\{x\}$, thus the paths of those subhypercubes not containing C^* are the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Hence, (19) remains true.

By our definition of C^* , the subhypercube of C^{**} that contains C^* was already occupied prior to addition of $\{x\}$, thus the set of subhypercubes of C^{**} that were occupied before and after addition of $\{x\}$ are identical. Hence, the APPROX-TSP-tour run on the center points of occupied subhypercubes of C^{**} is the same. Thus only the single edge connecting the path of the subhypercube containing C^* to the rest of the path of C^{**} may be different. Hence,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**}))) \right| \leq 1 \quad (22)$$

Thus by substituting (22) and (19) into (16),

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{**})) \right| \leq ((2^d - 1) \vee \tau) + 1 = 2^d \vee (\tau + 1) \quad (23)$$

3.3 Third Level Hypercube (k = 3) and Beyond

Going further in Case 2 in which $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated at the terminal end of $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$, let us consider C^{***} . Once again, there are two subcases for how $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$.

Subcase 1: If $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into the interior $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$, $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is now attached to the the path of a subhypercube of C^{***} that does not contain C^{**} . Since only the subhypercube of C^{***} that contains C^* is affected by the addition of $\{x\}$. Thus only the subhypercube containing C^{**} is affected, the other $2^d - 1$ subhypercubes are unaffected. By (23), we get the upper bound on the difference of test statistics for the subhypercube of C^{***} containing C^{**} . Hence,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***} \cup \{x\}))) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1) \quad (24)$$

By the definition of C^{**} , the subhypercube of C^{***} containing C^{**} was already occupied prior to addition of $\{x\}$. Thus, the result of running of APPROX-TSP-tour on the center points of occupied subhypercubes of C^{***} is the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Now consider the two edges needed to connect the path of the subhypercube containing $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$ to $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$. There is also a case where only one edge is required, and this is addressed prior to discussions of Edge 1 and Edge 2.

Single Edge Required: There is the edge case that the path of the subhypercube of C^{***} that contains C^{**} is at the terminal portion of $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$ in such a way that the path of $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is in the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$, this would require the formation of only 1 new edge, which may be different before and after addition of $\{x\}$

Edge 1: One of the terminal ends of the path of the subhypercube of C^{***} that contains C^{**} is $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$. The edge needed to link $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ to path of some of subhypercube of C^{***} that does not contain C^{**} may be different.

Edge 2: Now consider the other terminal end of the path of the subhypercube that contains C^{**} , which is not $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$, rather it is the edge formed between the path of some subhypercube of C^{**} that does not contain C^* (let us denote said subhypercube of C^{**} as O) and the path of some other subhypercube of C^{***} (let us denote the identity of the other subhypercube of C^{***} as D). We now make use of [Lemma 1.1](#) which states the following (proof provided in [Section 3.2.1](#))

Lemma 1.1. *With C^* defined as above, let us define C^{k*} as the smallest hypercube containing $C^{(k-1)*}$ and another occupied subhypercube that does not contain $C^{(k-1)*}$ for $k \geq 3; k \in \mathbb{Z}$. Consider the edge e is that is the edge formed by linking the subhypercube of C^{k*} that does not contain $C^{(k-1)*}$ (denote this subhypercube of C^{k*} as D) to the subhypercube of C^{k*} that does contain $C^{(k-1)*}$ and more specifically, this edge e is the edge formed between the path of D and a subhypercube of $C^{(k-1)*}$ that does not contain C^* (denote this subhypercube of $C^{(k-1)*}$ as O). This edge e is such that*

$$e \in \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*} \cup \{x\})), \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*})).$$

Applying [Lemma 1.1](#) to Edge 2, we see that the identity of edge e is the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Thus, from the scenarios presented above, we know there is at most one different edge from the scenarios of Single Edge Required and Edge 2. Hence,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***}))) \right| \leq 1. \quad (25)$$

By substituting (24) and (25) into the (17) for $k = 3$,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***})) \right| \leq (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (26)$$

Subcase 2: If $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is at the terminal end of $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$, then path of the subhypercube of C^{***} that contains C^{**} is also at the terminal end of $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$. C^{**} was defined in such a way that there are subhypercubes of C^{**} that are occupied and do not contain C^* . Since $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is at the terminal end of $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$, the other terminal end is a path of a subhypercube of C^{**} that does not contain C^* . It is this path of a subhypercube of C^{**} that does not contain C^* that links $\mathcal{H}(C^{**})$ to rest of $\mathcal{H}(C^{***})$. The edge e formed between some subhypercube of C^{***} that does not contain C^{**} and the subhypercube of C^{**} that does not contain C^* is such that $e \in \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***} \cup \{x\})), \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***}))$ by [Lemma 1.1](#). By the definition of C^{**} , the subhypercube of C^{***} containing C^{**} was already occupied. Thus, the result of running of APPROX-TSP-tour on the center points of occupied subhypercubes of C^{***} is the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Hence, the edges connecting the paths of the at most 2^d subhypercubes of C^{***} are the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Thus in this case,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***}))) \right| \leq 0. \quad (27)$$

The addition of $\{x\}$ does not affect any of the subhypercubes of C^{***} , apart from the single subhypercube that contains C^* . Hence, (24) holds. By substituting (24) and (27) into (17) for $k = 3$,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{***})) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1) \quad (28)$$

If there is $t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, such that $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$ and $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is not incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t-1)*})$, we utilise Lemma 1.2, which is proven in Section 3.2.2.

Lemma 1.2. *Suppose there is $t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, such that $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$ and $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is not incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t-1)*})$, for $2 \leq j \leq t - 1$*

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{j*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{j*})) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1). \quad (29)$$

Analyzing when $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$. Consider the 2 edges that incorporate $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t-1)*})$ into $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$. One edge is between $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ and path of subhypercube of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$ that does not contain C^* , and this edge maybe different before and after addition of $\{x\}$. The other edge is between the path of subhypercube of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$ that does not contain C^* and a portion of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t-1)*})$ that is not $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$. By Lemma 1.1, this edge was present before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Again, there is the edge case in which $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$ with only 1 edge needed in which $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t-1)*})$ is at the terminal of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$. Hence,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t*}))) \right| \leq 1 \quad (30)$$

Only the subhypercube of C^{t*} that contains $C^{(t-1)*}$ was affected by addition of $\{x\}$, hence,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t*}))) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1) \quad (31)$$

so using (36) and (31) in the triangle inequality (17) for $k = t$, we get

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})) \right| \leq 2^d + 1 \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (32)$$

Suppose there is no such t , then $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ remains at the terminal end of $\mathcal{H}(X \cup Y)$, using (36) whilst treating $t = \infty$

$$\left| T_{m,n}(X \cup Y \cup \{x\}) - T_{m,n}(X \cup Y) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1)$$

From (32), we see that $(2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2)$ is the upper bound of the difference in statistics to get $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ into the interior of some path. We now introduce another lemma, which is proven in Section 3.2.3.

Lemma 1.3. *Let t be the smallest integer for which $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is in the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$, we want to prove that for all $b \geq t$*

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{b*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{b*})) \right| \leq (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (33)$$

If there exists l such that $C^{l*} = [-2^S, 2^S]^d$, using Lemma 1.3, we get

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{l*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{l*}))) \right| \leq (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (34)$$

Since $(X \cup Y) \in [-2^S, 2^S]^d$, using (34)

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(X \cup Y \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(X \cup Y) \right| \leq (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (35)$$

Thus, if $\{x\}$ is added to $[-2^S, 2^S]^d$, $\gamma = (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2)$.

In the edge case of $\{x\}$ not being incorporated into $[-2^S, 2^S]^d$ cube. Let $M^* = \sup_{1 \leq j \leq d} |x_j|$ where x_j is the j^{th} coordinate of x and $S^* = \inf_{s \in \mathbb{Z}^+} \{s : 2^s \geq M^*\}$. Given that $\{x\}$ is not incorporated into the $[-2^S, 2^S]^d$ cube, we know $S^* > S$. Without loss of generality assume that $\{x\}$ gets incorporated into the i^{th} subhypercube ($1 \leq i \leq 2^d$) of the $[-2^{S^*}, 2^{S^*}]^d$ hypercube. There is at most a difference of 1 between the test statistics of the path in the i^{th} subhypercube of the $[-2^{S^*}, 2^{S^*}]^d$ hypercube, as it just involves connecting the previous path to point $\{x\}$. Connecting the paths of the 2^d subhypercubes of length 2^S requires at most $2^d - 1$ edges to link the 2^d subhypercubes. The difference in test statistics on these edges is $2^d - 1$, thus $\gamma = 1 + (2^d - 1) = 2^d$ in this case.

In any case of where $\{x\}$ is added to, $\gamma = (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2)$ is a constant bound on the difference between the test statistics. Hence, (10) holds for $\gamma = (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2)$ \square

3.4 Proof of Sublemmas

3.4.1 Proof of Lemma 1.1

Lemma 1.1. *With C^* defined as above, let us define C^{k*} as the smallest hypercube containing $C^{(k-1)*}$ and another occupied subhypercube that does not contain $C^{(k-1)*}$ for $k \geq 3; k \in \mathbb{Z}$. Consider the edge e is that is the edge formed by linking the subhypercube of C^{k*} that does not contain $C^{(k-1)*}$ (denote this subhypercube of C^{k*} as D) to the subhypercube of C^{k*} that does contain $C^{(k-1)*}$ and more specifically, this edge e is the edge formed between the path of D and a subhypercube of $C^{(k-1)*}$ that does not contain C^* (denote this subhypercube of $C^{(k-1)*}$ as O). This edge e is such that*

$$e \in \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*} \cup \{x\})), \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*})).$$

Proof. Since neither of these subhypercubes were affected by the addition of $\{x\}$, their associated paths are the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Since the result of running of APPROX-TSP-tour on the center points of occupied subhypercubes of C^{k*} is the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$, we know there must be an edge to connect the subhypercube of C^{k*} containing C^* to D before and after addition of $\{x\}$.

Now recall the formation of the path in $C^{(k-1)*}$, running APPROX-TSP-tour on the center points of occupied subhypercubes of C^{**} gives the ordering of the subhypercubes of C^{**} and since C^* , the hypercube containing $\{x\}$, was already occupied prior to addition of $\{x\}$, the ordering of the subhypercubes of $C^{(k-1)*}$ is the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Thus, the path of O is at the terminal end before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Thus, edge e is formed between the path of D and the path of O before and after addition of $\{x\}$ with the identities of the paths being unaffected by the addition of $\{x\}$. Hence, $e \in \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*} \cup \{x\})), \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{k*}))$ \square

3.4.2 Proof of Lemma 1.2

Lemma 1.2. *Suppose there is $t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, such that $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$ and $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is not incorporated into the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t-1)*})$, for $2 \leq j \leq t - 1$*

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{j*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{j*})) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1). \quad (36)$$

Proof. By (23) and (28), we have established that (36) is true for $j = 2, 3$. For the induction step, assume for some f such that $2 \leq f < t - 1$ that

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{f*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{f*})) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1) \quad (37)$$

We know by definition of t that $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is at the terminal end of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*})$, the edge needed to link the path of the subhypercube of $C^{(f+1)*}$ containing C^* to the rest of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*})$ is formed between the path of a subhypercube of $C^{(f+1)*}$ that does not contain C^* and a portion of $\mathcal{H}(C^{f*})$ that is not $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$, since $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is at the terminal end of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*})$. Applying Lemma 1.1, we get that

$e \in \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*} \cup \{x\})), \tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*}))$, hence

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*}))) \right| \leq 0 \quad (38)$$

We now study the difference in test statistics for the edges formed within the 2^d subhypercubes with

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*}))) \right| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{2^d} \left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*}_i))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*} \cup \{x\})_i)) \right| \quad (39)$$

Since only the subhypercube containing C^{f*} was affected by the addition of $\{x\}$, $2^d - 1$ of the terms on the right hand side of (39) are 0. For the subhypercube containing C^{f*} , we use inducton step of (37) to establish the following upperbound

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*}))) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1) \quad (40)$$

Hence, substituting (38) and (40) into the triangle inequality (17) for $k = f + 1$, we get

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(f+1)*})) \right| \leq 2^d \vee (\tau + 1).$$

By mathematical induction, (36) is true for $2 \leq j \leq t - 1$. \square

3.4.3 Proof of Lemma 1.3

Lemma 1.3. *Let t be the smallest integer for which $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$ is in the interior of $\mathcal{H}(C^{t*})$, we want to prove that for all $b \geq t$*

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{b*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{b*})) \right| \leq (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (41)$$

Proof. We will use induction to prove that for $i \geq 0$

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+i)*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+i)*})) \right| \leq 2^d + 1 \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (42)$$

From (32), we have the base case of $i = 0$. For the induction hypothesis, assume that for some $q \geq 0$,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q)*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q)*})) \right| \leq 2^d + 1 \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (43)$$

In the formation of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q+1)*})$, there is either one or two edges needed to connect $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q)*})$ to the rest of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q+1)*})$. In any case, the edges are formed between the path of a subhypercube of $C^{(t+q+1)*}$ that does not contain C^* and a portion of the path $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q)*})$ that is not $\mathcal{H}(C^*)$. Hence, the edge was present before and after addition of $\{x\}$ by Lemma 1.1. Thus the edges needed to connect $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q)*})$ to the rest of $\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q+1)*})$ are the same before and after addition of $\{x\}$. Given that APPROX-TSP-Tour returns the same path before and after addition of $\{x\}$ and that all of subhypercubes of $C^{(t+q+1)*}$ are unaffected except the one containing C^* , for all of the linkages between the 2^d hyperhypercubes except the ones linking the subhypercube of $C^{(t+q+1)*}$ containing C^* , there is the same linkage of paths of subhypercubes of $C^{(t+q+1)*}$ which contain the same paths. Thus,

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q+1)*} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{B}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(t+q+1)*}))) \right| \leq 0 \quad (44)$$

All of paths of the the 2^d subhypercubes of $C^{(b+q+1)*}$ are unaffected by the addition of $\{x\}$ except the one containing C^* . Hence, considering

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t+q+1} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t+q+1}))) \right| \leq \sum_{i=1}^{2^d} \left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t+q+1})_i)) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t+q+1} \cup \{x\})_i)) \right|, \quad (45)$$

all terms of the right hand side of (45) are 0 except the subhypercube containing C^{t+q} . Hence, by the induction hypothesis of (43), we have

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t+q+1} \cup \{x\}))) - T_{m,n}(\tilde{W}(\mathcal{H}(C^{t+q+1}))) \right| \leq 2^d + 1 \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (46)$$

Substitution of (44) and (46) into the triangle inequality gives

$$\left| T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(b+q+1)*} \cup \{x\})) - T_{m,n}(\mathcal{H}(C^{(b+q+1)*})) \right| \leq (2^d + 1) \vee (\tau + 2) \quad (47)$$

Thus, (41) holds. \square

3.5 Proof of Lemma 2

Lemma 2. For $\phi, \phi_1, \phi_2, \dots$ distribution functions with the same support such that $\frac{\phi_t}{\phi} \rightarrow 1$ uniformly on the set $\{z \in \mathbb{R}^d \mid \phi(z) > 0\}$. Let $\mathbb{Z}_t = \{Z_{1,N}, \dots, Z_{N,N}\}$ be IID with distribution ϕ_t . Let $h : \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow [0, 1]$ a measurable function such that almost all points $z \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is Lebesgue point of $h(z, \cdot)\phi(\cdot)$. Combined with the assumption that

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}(\exists j \in [N] \text{ s.t. } Z_{1,N} \rightarrow Z_{j,N} \in \mathcal{H}, \|Z_{1,N} - Z_{j,N}\| > aN^{-1/d}) = 0 \quad (48)$$

which essentially states that the probability of having long edges (edges longer than $aN^{-1/d}$) converges to 0.

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{1 \leq i \leq j \leq N} h(Z_{i,N}, Z_{j,N}) \mathbf{I}_{[Z_{i,N} \rightarrow Z_{j,N} \in \mathcal{H}]} \right] = \frac{\delta}{2} \int h(z, z) \phi(z) dz \quad (49)$$

with

$$\Delta(Z_{1,N}; \mathcal{H}(Z_N)) \xrightarrow{P} \delta, \quad (50)$$

Proof. We will present the proof of (48) in a following section. Assuming that (48) is true, the proof of (49) follows exactly from the proof of Proposition 1 of (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016). The proof of Proposition 1 in (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016) is independent of graph structure. Note that given the graph structure of the SHP means almost every node has degree 2, hence $\delta = 2$. Hence,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{1 \leq i \leq j \leq N} h(Z_{i,N}, Z_{j,N}) \mathbf{I}_{[Z_{i,N} \rightarrow Z_{j,N} \in \mathcal{H}]} \right] = \frac{\delta}{2} \int h(z, z) \phi(z) dz = \int h(z, z) \phi(z) dz \quad (51)$$

\square

3.5.1 Non-existence of Long Edges

We will now prove (48)

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{P}(\exists j \in [N] \text{ s.t. } Z_{1,N} \rightarrow Z_{j,N} \in \mathcal{H}, \|Z_{1,N} - Z_{j,N}\| > aN^{-1/d}) = 0$$

Proof. The proof of this sublemma is analogous to section 4.1 of (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016) for the minimal weight non-bipartite matching and utilizes very similar preliminaries and techniques with

alterations made to account for the differences between a Hamiltonian path and a minimal weight non-bipartite graph. Like (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), we consider the shortest Hamiltonian path \mathcal{H}^* associated with $\hat{\sigma}$ such that

$$\hat{\sigma} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \lambda(\|Z_{\sigma(i)} - Z_{\sigma(i+1)}\|) \quad (52)$$

with preliminaries of $\lambda : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ being a non-decreasing with $\lim_{b \rightarrow \infty} \lambda(b) < \infty$ such that $\lambda(b) \asymp b^\alpha$, $b \rightarrow 0$ for some $\alpha \in (0, d)$. Again like (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), for arbitrary $\epsilon > 0$, let us construct $r > 0$ such that for hypercube $A = [-r, r]^d$, we have

$$\int_A \phi > 1 - \epsilon.$$

Given that $\frac{\phi_N}{\phi} \rightarrow 1$, we know that there exists N_0 such that $\forall n \geq N_0$ for which we have

$$\int_A \phi_n > 1 - 2\epsilon.$$

Let $\hat{\sigma}$ be the associated permutation with the shortest Hamiltonian path \mathcal{H}^* . As in (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), let $K_N = \{k \in [N] : Z_{k,N} \notin A\}$. We will construct a shortest Hamiltonian approximation $\tilde{\mathcal{H}}$ associated with $\tilde{\sigma}$. For $k \in K_N$, we will set $\tilde{\sigma}(k)$ such that it connects the points $k \in K_N$ in increasing order of the first coordinate. Ties can be broken by considering the next coordinate. As in (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), let s_0 be the largest integer such that $2^{s_0 d} \leq N$ and consider

Fig. 3 $N = 18$, $d = 2$, $s_0 = 2$ (a) First iteration prior to linking nodes (b) Linking of nodes in first iteration in increasing order of horizontal coordinate (c) 2nd iteration of linking paths or points (d) Final Connection

the partition of A into $2^{s_0 d}$ hypercubes of side length $2r2^{-s_0}$. We will define $\tilde{\sigma}$ such that points in the same hypercube of length $2r2^{-s_0}$ will be linked together by the permutation $\tilde{\sigma}$ in increasing order of 1^{st} coordinate with ties being broken by the next coordinate. We have formed edges that have weight at most $2r2^{-s_0}\sqrt{d}$, the diameter of each of the hypercubes. To construct an upper bound on the number of edges of weight $2r2^{-s_0}\sqrt{d}$, the most we can construct is N in the case they are all N points are in the same hypercube. Since, there is at most N edges with each edge bounded by the diameter of the hypercube, hence the upper bound for connecting points within the length $2r2^{-s_0}$ hypercubes is

$$N \cdot \lambda(2r2^{-s_0}\sqrt{d})$$

We are now left with at most $2^{s_0 d}$ singular points or paths. Using a coarser partition of A as in the regime of (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), we will divide A into $2^{(s_0-1)d}$ hypercubes each of length $2r2^{-(s_0-1)}$ and diameter $2r2^{-(s_0-1)}\sqrt{d}$. We will now connect points or paths within hypercubes of diameter $2r2^{-(s_0-1)}\sqrt{d}$. Connecting of the points or paths in the hypercube can be done iteratively. Consider the point or terminal point in a path with the greatest first coordinate. If it is a point, connect it to a point or terminal point in a path with the least first coordinate excluding said point. If it is a path, connect the other terminal point to a point or terminal in a path with the greatest first coordinate

excluding said path. For both paths and points, ties can be broken by considering the next coordinate. This process can be done iteratively until all points are connected into a path within the hypercube of diameter $2r2^{-(s_0-1)}\sqrt{d}$. Similar to above, when forming edges of weight $2r2^{-(s_0-1)}\sqrt{d}$, we form at most 2^{s_0d} of them in the case that all points are located in the same hypercube. Thus, the upper bound of edges needed to connect points or paths within the length $2r2^{-(s_0-1)}$ hypercubes is

$$2^{s_0d} \cdot \lambda(2r2^{-(s_0-1)}\sqrt{d}).$$

This is be done iteratively until it is guaranteed that all points in A are connected into a single path to get the upper bound of forming edges in this manner for the points in A . Hence,

$$\sum_{k \notin K_N} \lambda(\|Z_{k,N} - Z_{\hat{\sigma}(k),N}\|) \leq N \cdot \lambda(2r2^{-s_0}\sqrt{d}) + 2^{s_0d} \cdot \lambda(2r2^{-(s_0-1)}\sqrt{d}) + 2^{(s_0-1)d} \cdot \lambda(2r2^{-(s_0-2)}\sqrt{d}) + \dots + 2^d \cdot \lambda(2r\sqrt{d})$$

The terminal point of the path outside of A with the greatest first coordinate connects to the terminal point of the path of points inside of A that has the greatest 1^{st} coordinate. Ties can be broken with the next coordinate. Hence, we have defined an approximation $\tilde{\sigma}$ that creates a Hamiltonian path. Again in the regime of (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016), using the definition of (52): $\Lambda(\mathbb{Z}_N, \hat{\sigma}) \leq \Lambda(\mathbb{Z}_N, \tilde{\sigma})$. To study $\Lambda(\mathbb{Z}_N, \tilde{\sigma})$ more:

$$\Lambda(\mathbb{Z}_N, \hat{\sigma}) \leq \Lambda(\mathbb{Z}_N, \tilde{\sigma}) \leq \sum_{k \in K_N} \lambda(\|Z_{k,N} - Z_{\hat{\sigma}(k),N}\|) + \sum_{k \notin K_N} \lambda(\|Z_{k,N} - Z_{\tilde{\sigma}(k),N}\|)$$

$$\Lambda(\mathbb{Z}_N, \hat{\sigma}) \leq \Lambda(\mathbb{Z}_N, \tilde{\sigma}) \leq \sum_{k \in K_N} \lambda(\|Z_{k,N} - Z_{\hat{\sigma}(k),N}\|) + N \cdot \lambda(2r2^{-s_0}\sqrt{d}) + 2^{s_0d} \cdot \lambda(2r2^{-(s_0-1)}\sqrt{d}) + 2^{(s_0-1)d} \cdot \lambda(2r2^{-(s_0-2)}\sqrt{d}) + \dots + 2^d \cdot \lambda(2r\sqrt{d}) \quad (53)$$

Equation (53) exactly matches (19) of the proof of Proposition 2, and the remainder of the proof is graph structure independent (Arias-Castro & Pelletier, 2016). \square

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